

Deliverable D3.4

Leveraging the need for indicators: An Outline Report

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Deliverable	D3.4 Leveraging the need for indicators: An Outline Report
Version	Version 2 of 9 December 2025
Work Package	WP3 EOV-based ocean indicators for climate
Due Date	30 April 2025
Submission Date	23 April 2025
Submission Date Version 2	9 December 2025 Changes introduced: Integration of the last publication in the list of the References, since the paper has been published.
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
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1. Publishable summary

Global climate indicators are used to describe and monitor the state of the climate. Five of the seven 'state-of-the-climate' indicators used by the World Meteorological Organisation relate to the ocean, highlighting the significant impact of the ocean on the climate, including ocean surface temperature, sea level, ocean heat content, sea ice extent, and ocean acidification. The ObsSea4Clim project focuses on physical ocean indicators, which are crucial for climate understanding.

Ocean indicators are necessary as they transform complex ocean data into simple and useful measures of the ocean's state and climate, which, combined with science-based knowledge, can inform policymakers and other stakeholders, ultimately supporting decision-making for a sustainable future and benefiting both society and the economy.

Six science-based quality criteria have been identified that ocean indicators should have: verified, significant, scalable, justified, measurable, and accessible. Indicators should be expertly assessed against these criteria to establish if they are scientifically mature and ready for implementation. This will help ensure the scientific robustness.

One of the challenges in ObsSea4Clim is to define the proposed ocean indicators for the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) such as sea surface temperature (SST), subsurface temperature, sea surface height, and sea ice and to regionalise the indicators. Regionalised ocean indicators help understanding which regions exhibit unique oceanic and climatic patterns, the factors driving these patterns, and how they relate to global trends.

For each proposed ocean indicator, the regions were identified, including both the global perspective, where relevant, and then progressively smaller regions

and seas. Thematic regions are also included for some indicators. Legislative exclusive economic zones (EEZ) will be analysed in specific case studies. For each ocean indicator, the proposed measures and associated data have been identified and will now be analysed on a regionalised basis and tested as part of the project for scientific robustness by the relevant lead institution in each case.

Extreme ocean indicators have also been identified. An extreme event in the ocean occurs when a physical or biogeochemical variable crosses a threshold that has a tangible impact on a physical process, ecosystem health, or the economy. Three target extremes have been identified: extreme temperature (or marine heatwaves - MHWs), extreme sea ice and extreme sea level.

A key conclusion of the discussions has been to promote the testing of several definitions for each of the extreme indicators rather than attempt to find one universal indicator. Accordingly, the ongoing work within the project will promote a framework for extreme indicator definition, in which key parameters and characteristics can be chosen on a case-by-case basis.

2. Introduction

2.1 Introduction to climate and ocean indicators

Global climate indicators are key parameters used to describe and monitor the changing climate, e.g. https://climatedata-catalogue-wmo.org/climate_indicators. They provide a picture of the state of the climate system and help track climate change across different domains.

The WMO uses 7 'state-of-the-climate' indicators that are based on the 54 Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) Essential Climate variables. 5 of the 7 'state-of-the-climate' indicators are ocean indicators, highlighting the fundamental impact of the ocean on climate; ocean surface temperature, sea level, ocean heat content, sea ice extent and ocean acidification and considered the core ocean indicators for assessing the state of the climate

Fig. 1: WMO 'State-of-the-climate' indicators, Ref: https://climatedata-catalogue-wmo.org/climate_indicators

The project scope for ObsSea4Clim covers the physical ocean indicators (Ocean Heat, Sea level and Sea Ice) whilst the sister projects BioEcoOcean and BioGeoSea cover biological and geochemical ocean indicators respectively.

2.2. Why do we need ocean indicators

Ocean indicators take complex ocean data and turn it into simple and useful measures of the state of the ocean and climate. They are a useful tool for regular reporting on the state, variability and change of the ocean and help forge multi-disciplinary collaboration. The ocean indicators together with science-based knowledge help inform effective decision making and beyond (von Schuckmann et al., 2020). Ocean indicators are a powerful tool to establish a dialogue at the science policy interface, in support of decision making and for sustainable development.

Fig. 2: The role of ocean monitoring and reporting to support and provide benefits to society and the economy. From von Schuckmann et al., 2020, J. of Marine Policy.

Figure 2 highlights the role of ocean monitoring and reporting and the added-value chain from raw products (remote sensing, in situ) to oceanographic science knowledge (including models) to high-quality data products and ocean indicators, which are used for reporting. These added-value products can provide the evidence basis for agencies and reporting bodies, decision makers, other stakeholders and the public, yielding societal and economic benefit (von Schuckmann et al., 2020).

Fig. 3: The need for ocean indicators.

Providing more detail, Figure 3 highlights the 8 core areas where ocean indicators can add value.

- **Observing system capacity:** For example, our observing capacity is good for sea surface temperature in the North Atlantic, but not as good at subsurface temperature at 2000m in the Southern Ocean.
- **Forecast and Model:** Ocean indicators can assist with model validation and forecasting accuracy
- **Ocean and climate assessments and reporting:** Focusing on the same indicators over time and specific regions helps to build up a coherent and comprehensive picture of how the ocean and climate health is changing.
- **Ocean literacy and communication:** Focusing consistently on key ocean indicators will help to build society’s knowledge of the ocean, ocean health, and the important role the ocean plays in climate.
- **Ocean climate nexus and governance:** Focus on the key ocean indicators which influence climate will help to provide focus in this complex area.
- **International and multi-to-transdisciplinary collaboration:** For example, the blue economy plays an essential role in supporting society. SST is used for coastal fisheries and coral reef management and sub-surface

temperature is linked to marine organisms and ecosystem function. A transdisciplinary approach to monitoring oceanographic data is very helpful in the management of living marine resources.

- **Research priority areas:** Ocean indicators help to highlight research gaps that may become areas of research focus, such as the subpolar gyre warming hole in the North Atlantic.

2.3 Requirements of an ocean indicator

The GOOS cross-panel task team on ocean indicators has identified six science-based quality criteria, using the climate and biodiversity indicator criteria (WMO, 2017; BIP document) as a starting point. An ocean indicator should also meet each of the 6 criteria (von Schuckmann et al., 2025, submitted): verified, significant, scalable, justified, measurable, and accessible.

Ocean indicators should only be endorsed as **verified** if they are based on a solid theoretical foundation, rigorously evaluated, and peer-reviewed for accuracy and reliability. To be **significant**, they must be grounded in a robust scientific framework, accounting for uncertainties that affect their interpretation. Indicators should be **scalable** across various spatial and temporal scales, and based on interoperable data that integrates with other systems for easy comparison and analysis. They must be **justified** and relevant for decision-making, **accessible** to a wide audience, and presented clearly for practical use. Indicators should be **measurable**, quantifiable, and derived from established frameworks with international coordination. Finally, they should be regularly updated, respecting data sovereignty and ethical considerations, while adhering to FAIR and CARE principles, and include historical, current, and forecast data for informed planning.

It is then proposed (Von Schuckmann et al., 2025, submitted) that each indicator undergoes expert assessment, first of its scientific maturity, criteria 1-3 (verified, significant and scalable), then for its readiness for implementation, Criteria 4-6 (justified, measurable and accessible). The process will determine if the indicator is concept, pilot or mature (UNESCO, 2012). The process will help ensure endorsed indicators are scientifically robust.

3. Regionalisation of Ocean Indicators

3.1 The need for regionalised ocean indicators

The ObsSea4Clim project is concerned with the physical ocean indicators, which are essential for climate. Some of the main EOVs for climate are sea surface temperature (SST), subsurface temperature, sea surface height, and sea ice. One of the challenges in ObsSea4Clim is to define the proposed indicators for the EOV and to regionalise the indicators.

Regionalised ocean indicators offer many benefits, including helping understand how various regions exhibit unique environmental, oceanic, and climatic patterns, the specific factors driving these differences, and how they relate to global trends. By equipping policymakers and stakeholders with accurate and region-specific data, regionalised ocean indicators can effectively support the development of tailored policies that address local environmental challenges, thus elevating essential ocean observations to the science and policy interface (von Schuckmann et al., 2020).

3.2 Process of Agreement

A meeting of ObsSea4Clim partners was convened on the 5th of July 2024 to agree on a set of regionalisations and variables. The meeting also discussed the scientific requirements surrounding regionalisation, including the underlying oceanic and climatic dynamics that contributed to these differences. This aimed to enhance our understanding of the mechanisms at play.

It was highlighted that remote regions had far-reaching impacts and that this was key for communicating the importance of ocean indicators that may at first seem removed from the region of interest. For example, a slowdown in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) could lead to significant climatic changes in Europe, including cooler temperatures and altered weather patterns (Meccia et al., 2024). Warmer-than-average ocean temperatures in the North Atlantic can have cascading effects on the climate (e.g. Sutton and Dong, 2012) and marine ecosystems (e.g. Edwards

et al., 2021) in Europe, influencing weather patterns, fish migration, and the overall health of marine biodiversity, which impacts the fishing industry and coastal communities. The extent and condition of Arctic Sea ice play a crucial role in regulating the climate of mid-latitude regions. Changes in sea ice could disrupt atmospheric circulation patterns, leading to extreme weather events and shifts in seasonal climate norms (e.g. Chripko et al., 2021). Additionally, changes in ocean circulation leading to Atlantification in the Arctic, where warmer Atlantic waters penetrated the Arctic Ocean, have altered its temperature and salinity. This has profoundly affected Arctic ecosystems, ice cover, and, potentially, global climate patterns (Ingvaldsen et al., 2021), highlighting the interconnectedness of regional and global systems.

3.3 Agreed regions and proposed indicators

For each EOVS which will be analysed, e.g., sea surface temperature, subsurface temperature, sea surface height, and sea ice, the proposed indicators were identified through discussions and meetings and are detailed in the tables below. For each proposed indicator, the proposed regions were identified, including both the global perspective, where relevant, and progressively smaller regions and seas. Thematic regions are also included for some indicators. Legislative exclusive economic zones (EEZ) will be analysed in specific case studies, including Ireland and Finland, for SST. The main hurricane development region in the Atlantic (10–20° N and 20–60° W) will be analysed for SST and ocean heat content, as there are direct links with rising ocean temperatures and hurricane intensity in the Atlantic.

The EOVS and associated indicators have been broken down into smaller regions as relevant; the North Atlantic Ocean (Fig 4. A), the Northeastern Atlantic and adjacent seas (Fig 4. B), the Arctic Ocean (Fig 5. A), and the Antarctic Ocean (Fig 5. B),. Figure 6 (A) shows a breakdown of the Northeastern Atlantic and adjacent seas in subregions, with case study regions shown in Fig. 6B. As part of the work planned, each proposed indicator will be assessed for its robustness in line with the requirements criteria outlined in 2.3 above.

Fig. 4: Maps of regions referred to in the text: (A) North Atlantic Ocean (red) with the Main Development Region for Hurricanes (Black box) and Gulf Stream Region (Blue box) highlighted. (B) Northeastern Atlantic and adjacent seas (orange). Ref: <https://sp.copernicus.org/articles/4-osr8/2/2024>

3.3.1 Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Temperature

Table 1: Agreed Sea Surface Temperature variables and regions.

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies
SST	SST	Mean SST	Copernicus Datasets Observational datasets including HadISST, and DCENT.	1980-present 1850-present	Northeast Atlantic Ocean and the adjacent Seas [MOI] North Atlantic [NUIM]	Mediterranean[MOI] Black Sea [MOI] Baltic [MOI] IBI* [MOI] Nordic [DMI, HAV] Barents Sea [NERSC] *IBI = Ireland, Biscay, Iberia	Legislative Bounds (EEZ, territorial waters): Ireland and Finland [NUIM, FMI] Thematic (Hurricane Main development Region) [NUIM]
SST	SST and sea ice temperature	Mean SST/IST	C3S Global L4 SST/IST	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic/global [DMI]		

Fig. 5: Extent of regions (A) Arctic Oceans (another common definition is $>60^{\circ}\text{N}$) and (B) Antarctic Ocean ($>60^{\circ}\text{S}$).

Fig. 6: Sub-regions referred to in the text. (A) North Sea (white), IBI (yellow, IBI = Ireland Biscay Iberia = OSPAR regions III, IV, V), Mediterranean Sea (purple), Black Sea (orange), Baltic Sea (blue), Nordic Sea (dark orange), Barents Sea (dark green). (B) Case studies referred to in the text: Irish continental shelf (red line) and Irish EEZ (green), Finnish EEZ (cyan).

Table 2: Variables and Regions associated with Sea Ice Surface Temperature.

EOV/ECV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice Surface temperature	Sea Ice Surface Temperature	Mean IST	AASTI/C3S L3/L4 [DMI]	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic sea ice [DMI]
			neXtSIM reanalysis, Copernicus datasets	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
Sea Ice Surface temperature	Melt Days	Days when the mean temperature is 0 °C or warmer	AASTI/C3S L3/L4 [DMI]	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic sea ice [DMI]
Sea Ice Surface temperature	Freezing degree days (FDD)	The cumulative FDD is usually calculated as a sum of average daily degrees below freezing	AASTI/C3S L3/L4 [DMI]	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic sea ice [DMI]

3.3.2 Subsurface Temperature

Table 3: Variables and Regions associated with Subsurface Temperature.

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Subsurface Temperature	Ocean Heat Content	Ocean Heat Content	Copernicus reanalysis - global and regional	1980- present (satellite)	NE Atlantic Ocean and adjacent seas [MOI] North Atlantic [MOI] Global [MOI and others]	Mediterranean [MOI] Barents Sea [NERSC] Black Sea[MOI] Baltic [MOI] IBI [MOI] Nordic[DMI, HAV] NWS[MOI]	MDR [NUIM] Gulf Stream/AMOC and Atlantic OHC [NUIM]
Subsurface Temperature	Marine Heatwaves	Subsurface Temperatures	Copernicus reanalysis - regional	1982-present	Mediterranean Sea [CMCC]		Subsurface marine heatwaves
				1993-present	Baltic Sea [FMI] Barents Sea [NERSC]		

*precise definition of subsurface MHWs (e.g. using OHC) will be dependent on the findings of 3.2.

3.3.3 Sea Ice

Table 4: Variables and Regions associated with Sea Ice Concentration.

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Concentration	Satellite-derived sea ice concentration	OSI-450a Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSMIS/SSMIS), release 3 OSI-458 Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (AMSR), release 3 ESA Sea Ice CCI: High(er) Resolution Sea Ice Concentration CDR, v3 NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1978-present (incl iCDR) 2002-present (incl iCDR) 1991-2020 1979-present	Arctic and Antarctic sea Ice [DMI]
		reXtSIM reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic and Antarctic sea Ice [NERSC]

		Satellite Passive microwave	Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSMI/SSMIS) and NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4 (1979 onwards)	1978-present	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		SAR	Sentinel-radar backscatter (2014) and EOS-04 RISAT-1 radar backscatter(2012)	Available images from 2014	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		Global reanalysis ensemble product	Copernicus Marine Services	1993-present	Arctic and Antarctic [CMCC]
		Satellite-derived	SIC from NOAA/NSIDC CDR, OSI SAF, ESA, CCI	1979-present/2002-2017	Arctic and Antarctic [CMCC]

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Extent	Satellite passive microwave	OSI-SAF version 3, Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMRR, SSMI, SSMIS) NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice concentration, version 4	1978/9-present	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
		Satellite	Arctic OMI SI extent obs, satellite observations	1979-present(satellite)	Arctic and Antarctic [MOI]

	<p>derived; ocean reanalysis and forecast</p>	<p>OSI SAF Sea ice index 1978-onwards, version 2.2 (2023), OSI-420. EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility.</p> <p>Antarctic_OMI_SI_extent_obs, satellite observations OSI SAF Sea ice index 1978-onwards, version 2.2 (2023), OSI-420. EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility.</p> <p>GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030, numerical models & GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024</p>	<p>1993-present (forecast and reanalysis)</p>	
	<p>Satellite-derived</p>	<p>OSI-450a Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS), release 3</p> <p>OSI-458 Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (AMSR), release 3</p> <p>ESA Sea Ice CCI: High(er) Resolution Sea Ice Concentration CDR, v3</p> <p>NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4</p>	<p>1978-present (incl iCDR)</p> <p>2002-present (incl iCDR)</p> <p>1991-2020</p> <p>1979-present</p>	<p>Arctic and Antarctic sea ice [DMI]</p>

Table 5: Variables and Regions associated with other Sea Ice Indicators.

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Drift	neXtSIM reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
		Buoy	International Arctic Buoy Programme (IABP)	1979-present	Arctic [FMI]
		Satellite Passive Microwave	Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSMI/SSMIS)	1978-present	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
		SAR	Sentinel-radar backscatter EOS-04, RISAT-1 radar backscatter	Available images since 2014 Available images since 2012	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
		Satellite passive microwave	NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
Sea Ice	Sea Ice thickness	In-situ observations	FMI monitoring programme	1898-present	Baltic/Bay of Bothnia [FMI]
		Global reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1993-present	Arctic and Antarctic [CMCC]

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Age	Satellite Derived and neXtSIM reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Area	Satellite Passive Microwave	Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS) and NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1978-present	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)	Sentinel-radar backscatter EOS-04, RISAT-1 radar backscatter	Available images from 2012 and 2014	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
	Sea Ice Area/ Freezeup/Break update/ Open water days	Satellite-derived	OSI-450a Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS), release 3 OSI-458 Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (AMSR), release 3 ESA Sea Ice CCI: High(er) Resolution Sea Ice Concentration CDR, v3 NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1978-present (incl iCDR) 2002-present (incl iCDR) 1991-2020 1979-present	Arctic and Antarctic sea ice [DMI]

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Sea Ice	Freezing Date/ Break update	In-situ observations	FMI monitoring programme	1898-present	Baltic/Bay of Bothnia
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Volume	neXtSIM	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]

3.3.4 Sea Surface Height

Table 6: Variables and Regions associated with Sea Surface Height.

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Surface Height	Sea Level	Mean Sea Level	Copernicus Satellite Observations and Reanalysis	1980-present 1950-present 1993-present	NE Atlantic Oceans and adjacent seas [MOI] Nordic and Barents Seas	Mediterranean [MOI] Barents Sea [NERSC] Black Sea [MOI], Baltic[MOI] IBI[MOI], Nordic[HAV, DMI], NWS[MOI]	Coastlines e.g.national/ regional Link between data e.g. Irish [NUIM]
Sea Surface Height	Sea level	Mass Component	GRACE GRACE/FO	2002-2017 2018-present	Global	Norwegian Continental shelf [NERSC] Arctic Ocean [NERSC]	Quantify open ocean contribution Norwegian sea level variations
Sea Surface Height	In-situ Sea Level	Tide Gauge	Monthly tide gauge data (PSMSL)	1800-present (but not complete)	Global coastline	Arctic Ocean	Assess the quality of the Arctic Ocean Physics reanalysis Topaz4b
			10 minute tide gauge data (Kartverket)	late 1980s-present (but not complete)	Norwegian Coast	Western and Central Norway	1) Assess the quality of satellite altimetry products (e.g., SWOT). 2) Characterize mesoscale variability over the Norwegian continental shelf

3.4 Examples of Regionalisation

3.4.1 Irish SST

Figure 7 shows the mean SST from 1982-2024 for the NE Atlantic, full Irish Continental Shelf Waters and Irish EEZ. Whilst the variability is fairly consistent between the areas over the time period, the territorial waters are up to 0.5°C warmer than the NE Atlantic over the period. The difference in temperature can be important for the location of fish species and when comparing across different data products.

Fig. 7: Annual Mean SST 1982-2024. North Eastern Atlantic (blue), Irish Territorial Waters (Green), Irish EEZ (red). Data NOAA OISST.

3.4.2 Using IST vs UISST (Under Ice SST)

Traditionally, sea surface temperature (SST) trends have been estimated only for the extra-polar (60°S – 60°N) ocean or globally using under-ice SSTs (UISST) in sea-ice covered regions. The UISST represents a proxy estimate of the water temperature just below the sea ice (usually assumed to be at the freezing point of sea water, ~ -1.8°C), and does not represent the actual surface temperature of the sea ice. The SST/UISST is thus a very poor indicator of the surface temperature changes in high latitudes. A more accurate and consistent way to monitor high-latitude surface temperature changes can

be obtained by combining SST with satellite sea-ice surface temperature (IST) observations. A new global gap-free combined SST and IST climate data record has recently been produced within C3S (soon to be released in the CDS), and the initial results show, as expected, a significant underestimation of the warming trend when using SST/UISST compared to the SST/IST combination. The results highlight the importance of using the best available indicators and constantly improving indicators (Englyst et al., in prep).

4. Extreme Indicators

4.1 The need for extreme indicators

An extreme event in the ocean occurs when a physical or biogeochemical variable crosses a threshold that has a tangible impact on physical processes, ecosystem health, or the economy. The threshold, and therefore the concept of extremity, depends hugely on context and objective. Extremes are typically also rare events, though their rate of occurrence may be modified on long-time scales, e.g., an increase in heatwaves due to global warming. However, the need to study extreme events and provide relevant indicators derives from the need to mitigate and communicate their potential impacts. The WMO Climate Indicators (Fig. 1) also include measures of extremes as “Additional Indicators” used to “..allow a more detailed picture of the changes in the respective domain”, currently limited to global average temperature and precipitation.

The three target extremes in ObsSea4Clim, **extreme temperature** (or marine heatwaves - MHWs), **extreme sea ice** and **extreme sea levels**, cause a wide and diverse range of impacts across ecosystems and economies. Extreme temperatures cause mass mortality events, aquaculture and fishery losses, and induce atmospheric extremes such as tropical cyclones (Capotondi et al., 2024). Extremes of sea ice ... Sea level extremes lead to inundation of residential areas and cultural heritage sites, accelerated coastal erosion, saltwater intrusions damaging to agriculture (Pinardi et al., 2024). Therefore, even within regions, there can be different requirements for indicators of extremes.

¹ https://climatedata-catalogue-wmo.org/climate_indicators# Last accessed 28th March 2025

Extreme event indicators fit clearly into the 8 core areas where ocean indicators can add value (Fig. 2). MHWs and sea ice loss events cross national waters and impact economies and ecosystems, requiring **international and multi- to transdisciplinary collaborations**. Studying the variability of extremes is a **research priority area** for many fields, such as building **forecasts and models**. Monitoring extremes makes specific demands of **observing system capacity**, such as the need for long-term and consistent historical data required to understand typical conditions, against which “extreme” can be defined. Extremes are symptoms of global warming, and in recent years have become integral to **ocean and climate assessments & reporting**. The precise definition of extremes goes beyond technical discussions (for example, on thresholds), and impacts key statistics used for **ocean literacy & communication** (Boxes 1 & 2). Extremes affect many types of stakeholders, are often linked to wider atmospheric or climate conditions, and therefore find themselves at the centre of the **ocean climate nexus** and should be considered across **ocean governance**.

4.2 Process of Agreement

In preparation for Milestone 5 (“Identification of Extreme Indicators”, delivered January 2025), discussions were held on the role of indicators for the three event types (extreme temperature, sea level and sea ice). For extreme temperature, there are many competing definitions (of marine heatwaves), all of which have value in different contexts (Box 2). For sea level, definitions of extremes depend also on the data source (i.e. in-situ coastal or satellite-derived open ocean). For sea ice, the utility of various statistical-based extremes of sea ice concentration and thickness must be compared to alternative indicators like open-ice days.

A key conclusion of the discussions so far has been to promote the testing of several definitions within the project, rather than attempting to find universal indicators. As a first step towards providing a framework and recommendations for user-relevant extreme definitions, project initiatives are being organised to test the sensitivity of key results to MHW definitions (Box 1). Instead of homing in on a specific or universal indicator for extremes, the project instead promotes a *framework for indicator definition*, in which key parameters and characteristics (such as contributing EOVs, or the type of climatology used; Table 7) can be chosen on a case-by-case basis.

Box 1. MHW Hackathon: Towards a framework for extreme temperature indicators

A Hackathon focused on defining MHWs was organised for project partners, taking place during the General Assembly in March 2025. Participants explored how different MHW definitions impact our interpretation of trends, event characteristics, and long-term climate assessments (e.g. global MHW coverage, Fig. 8). With growing interest from organizations like Copernicus, the results from the hackathon will also provide recommendations on defining MHW indicators in different contexts to ensure their relevance for future climate monitoring (See Section 4.3 for outcomes). The lessons learnt and recommendations resulting from the initiative will be used to inspire similar outcomes for sea level and sea ice.

Key Outcomes:

- Development of a new high-resolution global dataset of various climate-relevant MHW definitions.
- Initial steps toward establishing a framework for defining standardised MHW indicators, improving consistency in climate reporting.

Fig. 8: Global (70N – 70S) coverage of MHWs using the WMO baseline of 1991 – 2020. Standard 5-day minimum definition (WMO90; gold); 10-day minimum (blue), 30-day minimum (green), detrended SST (orange), and a 30-year moving average for data between 2011 and 2024 (purple). All SST data were obtained from OSTIA.

Table 7: Extreme Indicators. (*) indicates *proposed* EOVs. See Milestone 5 for detail

Extreme Indicator	EOVs	Temporal Resolution	Climatology Frequency	Climatology Type	Threshold	Metrics
Extreme Temperature (Marine Heatwaves)	SST, subsurface temperature, OHC	Daily	Daily	Fixed/Moving	90/95/99 th percentile	Occurrence, intensity (anomaly w.r.t threshold), duration, cumulative intensity, area
Extreme Sea Level	SSH	minute/hourly	Tidal	Fixed/Moving	Generalised extreme value theory (block maxima), and generalised Pareto distribution (above 97.5% threshold level)	Occurrence, Return level/period
		Daily	Annual	Fixed/Moving	99 th percentile	
Extreme Sea Ice Loss	Sea Ice (SIC, SIE)	Daily	Monthly	Fixed	90/95/99 th percentile	SIE defined as the area with SIC>15%, max and minimum extent (i.e. March + September), open water days
	Sea Ice (SIT)	weekly	weekly	Fixed	90/95/99 th percentile	Annual maximum ice thickness
	Sea/Ice surface temperature*	Daily	Daily/Monthly	Fixed	90/95/99 th percentile	Intensity (anomaly w.r.t threshold)

4.3 Towards a framework for extreme indicators

It is clear that there is no single definition of extremes that is relevant for all case studies or regions, and this is true for all three extremes targeted in the project. The widely used definition of MHWs, for example, requires an exceedance of the 90th-percentile for five or more days; although motivated by the fact that longer-lasting temperatures are likely to cause more damage, the precise numbers are quite arbitrary (Hobday et al., 2016). Studies of extremes in climate projections, a key component of ObsSea4Clim, require comparisons of the type of climatology used to define extremes (Box 2).

In all cases, stakeholder engagement will be key to understanding the relevant definitions of extreme. Already in the research communities, competing definitions are widely accepted, and efforts towards a universal approach are being redirected towards context-specific (case-by-case) definitions (e.g. Farchadi et al., 2025).

We are working towards a framework for defining extreme indicators, in which definitions (Table 7) can be modified to specific needs on a case-by-case basis. This requires deep knowledge of the problem at hand. Examples may include: working with fisheries to understand key regions and phenomena which impact stocks; understanding local coastal morphology to provide sea level indicators for erosion. The scope of ObsSea4Clim is to demonstrate the feasibility of this, not to provide many examples.

Flexibility and inter-comparison are key. Already within the project, competing definitions are being compared to test the robustness of results. There are, however, pitfalls to this approach. A range of definitions can also lead to potential confusion for wider groups of stakeholders, particularly for the general public. Considering the Gulf of Bothnia example (Box 2), do we communicate that MHWs will become more frequent with time or remain consistent? The fact that the answer is “both” is not clear to a non-technical audience.

Box 2. Case Study of marine heatwaves in the Gulf of Bothnia

An example of using different definitions in a complementary way is shown for the Gulf of Bothnia (Fig. 9). A 200-year time series of decadal MHW statistics is shown for a fixed climatology (Fig. 9, top) and a moving climatology (30 years prior to target year; Fig. 9, bottom). Fixed climatology events may be relevant for species with little ability to adapt, and demonstrates the role of long-term climate change. Meanwhile a moving climatology is more suited for studying species capable of adapting to background warming, and highlights more the inter-annual variability.

The information provided is fundamentally different, and in either cases MHW occurrence is increasing or remaining relatively stable; a difficult concept to communicate, both one crucial to the understanding of climate projections.

Fig. 9: Total number of MHW days during JJAS, grouped per decade, for Gulf of Bothnia stations Kemi and Ulkokalla. Observations from 1900-1976, reanalysis period from 1976-2006 and future projections 2006-2100. Model simulations of regional NEMO setup have been forced with three downscaled CMIP5 models (EC, MPI ESM LR and HadleyCenter GEM), under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Fixed climatology is selected as 30 years from the beginning of each dataset and moving climatology is based on a 30-year centred window.

5. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific objectives of the project.

#SO1	<p>To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOV/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing</p>
<p>Ocean indicators are necessary as they transform complex ocean data into simple and useful measures of the ocean's state and climate, which, combined with science-based knowledge, can inform policymakers and other stakeholders, ultimately supporting decision-making for a sustainable future and benefiting both society and the economy.</p> <p>This deliverable is a preliminary report on the work that will be further developed in D3.1 <i>Regionalised Indicators</i> and D3.2 <i>Extreme Indicators</i>. This deliverable paves the way for D3.1 and D3.2. It also builds on the already achieved milestones MS5 <i>Identification of extreme indicators for Task 3.2</i> and MS6 <i>Agreement of boundaries for a set of regionalisation approaches for a choice of ocean indicators for Task 3.1</i>.</p>	

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